

Synthesis of symmetrical and unsymmetrical α,ω -bi-(3,3''-flavonyloxy)alkanes

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Abstract : Several symmetrical α,ω -bi-(3,3''-flavonyloxy)alkanes (3a-w) have been synthesised by treatment of variously substituted flavonols (1) with α,ω -dibromoalkanes [Br-(CH₂)_n-Br, where n = 2 to 6] in the molar ratio 2 : 1. However, the reactants in the molar ratio 1 : 1 furnished a mixture of (3) and α -(3-flavonyloxy)- ω -bromoalkanes (4). The latter (4) on treatment with flavonols of different substitution pattern (5) gave unsymmetrical α,ω -bi-(3,3''-flavonyloxy)alkanes (6a-y).

Keywords : Biflavonyloxy alkanes, flavonol, α,ω -dibromoalkanes, synthesis.

Many naturally occurring and synthetic flavonoids are known¹ to have significant biological properties and pharmaceutical potencies. A number of flavone derivatives carrying a methoxy group at C-3 and hydroxyl at C-5 position are found to have antibiotic^{2,3}, anticancer and antiviral^{4,5} activity. Bischromones⁶ have shown wide range of biological activities.

Results and discussion

In continuation to our earlier studies⁷ the synthesis of biflavonyloxy alkanes wherein 3- and 3''-position of flavone nucleus is linked by polymethylenedioxy [-O-(CH₂)_n-O-; n = 2 to 6] group is reported hitherto as outlined in Scheme 1. Flavonols (1) and α,ω -dibromoalkanes (2) [Br-CH₂-(CH₂)_n-CH₂-Br; n = 0 to 4] in the molar ratio (2 : 1)] were heated under reflux (10-12 h) in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate in dry acetone or acetone + DMF mixture (2 : 1, v/v), to afford the symmetrical α,ω -bi-(3,3''-flavonyloxy)alkanes (2) in 40-60% yield (Table 1). IR spectra of these compounds show complete absence of hydroxyl stretching bands. Presence of carbonyl absorption around 1640-1650 cm⁻¹ and asymmetric and symmetric stretching bands of ether linkage (aryl-O-alkyl) in the regions 1280-1240 and 1060-1020 cm⁻¹ respectively is indicative of the proposed structure (3).

Compd.	R	R ₁	R ₂	n	M p (°C)	Yield (%)
3a	H	H	H	0	152	44
3b	H	H	OCH ₃	0	179	42
3c	CH ₃	H	H	0	165	45
3d	CH ₃	H	OCH ₃	0	178	40
3e	H	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	0	118	50
3f	H	OC ₂ H ₅	OCH ₃	0	120	47
3g	H	H	H	1	159-160	42
3h	H	H	OCH ₃	1	143-144	46
3i	H	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	1	109	63
3j	H	OC ₂ H ₅	OCH ₃	1	111	50
3k	CH ₃	H	OCH ₃	2	183-185	45
3l	H	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	2	177	62
3m	H	OC ₂ H ₅	OCH ₃	2	176	46
3n	H	H	H	3	127-128	42
3o	H	H	OCH ₃	3	134-135	48
3p	CH ₃	H	H	3	132-133	40
3q	H	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	3	111	56
3r	H	OC ₂ H ₅	OCH ₃	3	131	45
3s	H	H	H	4	144	40
3t	H	H	OCH ₃	4	112	46
3u	CH ₃	H	H	4	163	48
3v	H	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	4	155	60
3w	H	OC ₂ H ₅	OCH ₃	4	162	50

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- 4a R = Me, R₁ = R₂ = H, n = 1
- 4b R = Me, R₁ = H, R₂ = OMe, n = 1
- 4c R = H, R₁ = R₂ = OMe, n = 1
- 4d R = R₁ = R₂ = H, n = 2
- 4e R = Me, R₁ = H, R₂ = OMe, n = 2
- 4f R = H, R₁ = R₂ = OMe, n = 2
- 4g R = Me, R₁ = H, R₂ = OMe, n = 3
- 4h R = Me, R₁ = H, R₂ = OMe, n = 4

Scheme 1. Reagent : (A) Dry acetone/dry acetone-DMF (2 : 1), anhydrous K₂CO₃, reflux.

¹H NMR spectral studies of 3,3''-(polymethylenedioxy)-bis-(4',7-dimethoxyflavone) (**3i**), (**3l**), (**3q**) and (**3v**), in which polymethylenedioxy group [-O-CH₂-(CH₂)_n-CH₂-O-; n = 1 to 4] has a chain of three to six methylene

groups have been systematically carried out to ascertain the chemical shift values of methylene groups in symmetrical 3,3''-biflavonyloxy alkanes. The results have been presented in Table 2. Flavanols (**1**) and α,ω-

Table 2. ¹H NMR spectral data of **3i**, **3l**, **3q** and **3v**

Compd.	H-5,5''	H-6,6'', H-8,8'', H-3',5' and H-3''',5'''	OCH ₃ - 7,7''	H-2',6' and H-2''',6'''	OCH ₃ - 4',4'''	-O-CH ₂ -(CH ₂) _n -CH ₂ -O-
3i	8.08 (d)	6.89-6.95 (m)	3.91 (s)	7.98 (d)	3.34 (s)	n = 1; 2.13 (2H, t, -CH ₂ -), 4.15 (4H, t, 2 × -OCH ₂ -)
3l	7.92 (d)	6.73-6.89 (m)	3.78 (s)	7.82 (d)	3.74 (s)	n = 2; 1.6-1.9 (4H, m, 2 × -CH ₂ -), 3.90 (4H, t, 2 × -OCH ₂ -)
3q	7.96 (d)	6.82-7.05 (m)	3.90 (s)	8.0 (d)	3.85 (s)	n = 3; 1.20-1.90 (6H, m, 3 × -CH ₂ -), 3.99 (4H, t, 2 × -OCH ₂ -)
3v	7.98 (d)	6.78-6.91 (m)	3.80 (s)	7.89 (d)	3.75 (s)	n = 4; 1.10-1.80 (8H, m, 4 × -CH ₂ -), 3.90 (4H, t, 2 × -OCH ₂ -)

dibromoalkanes (**2**; $n = 1$ to 4) in the molar ratio ($1 : 1$) were heated under reflux in dry acetone or acetone-DMF mixture ($2 : 1$, v/v) in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate and the reaction was monitored till it gave negative test with alcoholic ferric chloride (8–12 h). The solid mass obtained after usual work up of the reaction mixture was digested with boiling ether and the ether insoluble compound was identified as symmetrical α,ω -bi-(3,3''-flavonyloxy)alkanes (**3**) and ether soluble component as α -(3-flavonyloxy)- ω -bromoalkanes (**4**) through m.m.p.s, co-tlc and superimposable IR spectra with authentic samples⁷. ¹H NMR spectra of (**4c**) showed characteristic signals for -O-CH₂-CH₂-CH₂-Br. A triplet centred near δ 4.05 equivalent to two protons is assigned to -OCH₂- group whereas a triplet centred near δ 3.44 is assigned to -CH₂-Br. The central -CH₂- group which is coupled to two different methylene groups is shown as quintet centred at δ 2.15. Methoxy protons at C-7 and C-4' integrating for six protons appear at δ 3.80 as singlet and aromatic protons as multiplets in the range δ 6.70–8.02. For compound (**4f**) signals at δ 4.02 (t, -OCH₂-), 3.45 (t, -CH₂-Br) and 1.60–2.20 (m, -(CH₂)₂-), 3.90 (s, $2 \times$ -OCH₃) and 6.88–8.09 (m, Ar-H) confirm the proposed structure.

Compounds (**4a-h**) on treatment with variously substituted flavonols (**5**) in the molar ratio ($1 : 1$) in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate and dry acetone/acetone + DMF ($2 : 1$, v/v) under refluxing conditions resulted unsymmetrical α,ω -bi-(3,3''-flavonyloxy)alkanes (**6**). IR spectra of these compounds showed ν_{\max} in the range 1640–1620 cm⁻¹ (C=O), 1270–1260 and 1040–1020 cm⁻¹ for asymmetric and symmetric aryl-O-alkyl ether linkage. Absorption arising from methylene stretching occurs at 2960–2840 cm⁻¹. Methylene scissoring and twisting frequencies in the range 1470–1450 and 1350–1150 cm⁻¹ are not very diagnostic due to overlapping with other group frequencies. ¹H NMR spectra of the unsymmetrical α,ω -bi-(3,3''-flavonyloxy)alkane (**6o**) showed a high field multiplets at δ 1.82 assigned to -(CH₂)₂- and a low field triplet at δ 4.02 assigned to $2 \times$ -O-CH₂- groups of tetramethylenedioxy group [-O-CH₂-(CH₂)₂-CH₂-O-]. The presence of methoxy groups at C-4' and C-4''' was revealed by a singlet at δ 3.88 whereas methoxy group at C-7 was characterised by a singlet at δ 3.90. A singlet at δ 2.45 revealed the presence of methyl group at C-6''. Two multiplets at δ 6.80–7.10 and 7.90–8.20 integrating for thirteen aromatic protons and a singlet at δ 7.40 showed the presence of proton at C-5''.

Experimental

All m.p.s were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Purity of the samples was checked by TLC using silica gel-G plates using ethyl acetate-benzene ($9 : 1$, v/v) or benzene alone as solvent systems. Visualisation of spots was done in iodine chamber or by spraying with aq. H₂SO₄ (10%). IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on DIGILAB FTS-14 or Perkin-Elmer 157 P spectrophotometer (ν_{\max} in cm⁻¹). ¹H NMR were recorded in CDCl₃ on a Varian CFT-20 or Bruker-DRX-300 (300 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal standard (chemical shifts in δ , ppm). All compounds gave satisfactory C and H analysis and IR spectra were in accord with the assigned structures.

Synthesis of symmetrical α,ω -bi-(3,3''-flavonyloxy)-alkanes (**3**) and α -(3-flavonyloxy)- ω -bromoalkanes (**4**) have been carried out as described in our earlier communications⁷. Table 1 gives the melting points and yields of the new compounds (**3a-w**). The compounds **3a-w** have been recrystallized using solvents (a) C₂H₅OH for **3b**, **3h**, **3i**, **3m**, **3q**, **3s** to **3w**; (b) C₆H₆ for **3a**, **3d**, **3g**, **3n**, **3o** and **3p**; (c) Me₂CO + C₂H₅OH for **3c**, **3e**, **3f**, **3j**, **3k**, **3l** and **3r**. Compounds **3d** and **3k** have been obtained as yellow crystalline compound whereas other are colorless.

The IR and ¹H NMR spectral data of **3a** and **3k** are given below :

3a : ν (cm⁻¹) : 1630 (C=O), 1240, 1080 (C-O-C); δ_{H} : 4.48 (4H, s, $2 \times$ -OCH₂-), 8.17 (2H, d, H-5,5''), 7.10–7.80 and 8.09 (16H, m, Ar-H).

3k : ν (cm⁻¹) : 1640 (C=O), 1260, 1040 (C-O-C); δ_{H} : 1.83 (4H, m, $2 \times$ -CH₂-), 2.43 (6H, s, $2 \times$ -CH₃), 3.85 (6H, s, $2 \times$ -OCH₃), 4.01 (4H, t, $2 \times$ -OCH₂-), 7.95 (2H, s, H-5,5''), 6.96–8.04 (14H, m, Ar-H).

General procedure for the synthesis of unsymmetrical α,ω -bi-(3,3''-flavonyloxy)alkanes (6a-y) :

A mixture of α -(3-flavonyloxy)- ω -bromoalkane (**4**) (0.015 mol) and substituted flavonol (**5**) (0.01 ml) and dry acetone/dry acetone + DMF ($2 : 1$, v/v) (50 ml) was refluxed for 8–12 h. After completion of the reaction as judged by negative test with alcoholic ferric chloride, the reaction mixture was filtered while still hot. The residue was washed with boiling acetone (3×30 ml). The combined filtrates was concentrated under reduced pressure. The separated solid on recrystallisation with solvents (a) CH₃OH + C₆H₆ ($2 : 1$) for **6a**, **6b**, **6c** and **6u**; (b) Me₂CO + C₂H₅OH for **6p**, **6t**, **6x** and **6y**; (c) C₂H₅OH (90%)

Table 3. Melting points and yields of 6a-y

Compd.	R	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	R ₅	R ₆	n	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)
6a	CH ₃	H	OCH ₃	H	H	H	H	1	130	92
6b	CH ₃	H	OCH ₃	H	H	H	OCH ₃	1	132	72
6c	CH ₃	H	OCH ₃	CH ₃	H	H	H	1	135	79
6d	H	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	CH ₃	H	H	OCH ₃	1	145	80
6e	H	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	H	H	H	OCH ₃	1	99	70
6f	H	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	CH ₃	H	H	CH ₃	1	138	63
6g	H	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	CH ₃	H	H	Cl	1	148	65
6h	H	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	H	OC ₂ H ₅	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	1	154	60
6i	H	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	H	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	1	109	55
6j	H	H	H	H	H	H	OCH ₃	2	99-100	92
6k	H	H	H	CH ₃	H	H	H	2	135-136	61
6l	H	H	H	CH ₃	H	H	OCH ₃	2	129	92
6m	CH ₃	H	OCH ₃	H	H	H	OCH ₃	2	130	85
6n	CH ₃	H	OCH ₃	CH ₃	H	H	H	2	183-185	92
6o	H	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	CH ₃	H	H	OCH ₃	2	155	60
6p	H	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	CH ₃	H	H	H	2	154	70
6q	H	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	H	H	H	OCH ₃	2	130	77
6r	H	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	H	H	H	H	2	144	68
6s	H	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	H	OC ₂ H ₅	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	2	174	68
6t	H	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	H	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	2	115	65
6u	CH ₃	H	OCH ₃	H	H	H	OCH ₃	3	111-112	71
6v	CH ₃	H	OCH ₃	CH ₃	H	H	H	3	128-130	92
6w	CH ₃	H	OCH ₃	H	H	H	H	4	102	85
6x	CH ₃	H	OCH ₃	H	H	H	OCH ₃	4	135-136	86
6y	CH ₃	H	OCH ₃	CH ₃	H	H	H	4	118-119	86

for 6d-f, 6i-m, 6o, 6q-s, 6v and 6w; (d) CH₃OH (90%) for 6g and 6h; (e) C₆H₆ for 6n afforded analytical samples of 6a-y. Compounds 6b, 6m, 6n, 6u, 6v and 6y are obtained as pale yellow, 6w as light brown whereas others are colorless. The melting points and yields of synthesised compounds are given in Table 3. IR and ¹H NMR spectral data of some members are given below :

6l : ν (cm⁻¹) : 1630 (C=O), 1280, 1040 (C-O-C); δ_{H} : 1.78 (4H, m, -(CH₂)₂-), 2.38 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.76 (3H, s, -OCH₃), 3.95 (4H, t, 2 × -OCH₂-), 6.8-8.15 (16H, m, Ar-H).

6p : ν (cm⁻¹) : 1640 (C=O), 1260, 1040 (C-O-C); δ_{H} : 1.80 (4H, m, -(CH₂)₂-), 2.48 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.89 (3H, s, 4'-OCH₃), 3.91 (3H, s, 7-OCH₃), 4.01 (4H, t, 2 × -OCH₂-), 6.80-8.20 (15H, m, Ar-H).

6q : ν (cm⁻¹) : 1640 (C=O), 1260, 1030 (C-O-C);

δ_{H} : 1.84 (4H, m, -(CH₂)₂-), 3.87 (6H, s, 2 × -OCH₃, at -4' and -4''), 3.90 (3H, s, -OCH₃ at C-7), 4.04 (4H, t, 2 × -OCH₂-), 6.80-8.30 (15H, m, Ar-H).

6w : ν (cm⁻¹) : 1640 (C=O), 1280, 1040 (C-O-C); δ_{H} : 1.28-1.62 (8H, m, -(CH₂)₄-), 2.35 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.75 (3H, s, -OCH₃), 3.92 (4H, m, 2 × -OCH₂-) and 6.8-8.15 (16H, m, Ar-H).

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